

**NATIONAL FOOD AUTHORITY – COMMUNITY PARTNERING
TOWARDS AN ENSURED FOOD SECURITY LOGISTICS
IN OCCIDENTAL MINDORO**

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National Food Authority – Community Partnering towards an Ensured Food Security Logistics in Occidental Mindoro

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Abstract

Rice is a highly political commodity as it is the main staple of the country. It has always been at the forefront of agricultural policies in government. Most of the strategies focus on fostering food self-sufficiency, providing rice farmers with high incomes, and making prices affordable to consumers (Tobias, Molina, Valera, Mottaleb, and Mohanty, 2012). On February 14, 2019, President Rodrigo R. Duterte signed the Rice Tariffication Law (RTL) titled “An Act liberalizing the importation, exportation, and trading of rice, lifting for the purpose the quantitative import restriction on rice, and for other purposes”. This is also known as the Rice Liberalization Act or Republic Act No. 11203, which amends the Agricultural Tariffication Act of 1996 that imposed tariffs on agricultural imports except for rice (Dansal, 2019). In order to ensure that our local farmers are able to cope with the competition among the commercial imported rice as stipulated in the liberalization act on rice as a primary commodity, NFA was given the function to ensure that farmers’ produce is still well accommodated as buffer stocks during emergencies and disasters. The main challenge that this capstone project would like to address is the difficulties confronted by NFA as it struggles to find enough storage logistics in the areas during the procurement period season. Quigley & Robertson (2015) underscored that the storage capacity is one of the most important logistics required for palay procurement operation. Establishing a collaborative program between the NFA and the community stakeholders ensures that there will be enough rice for the people, and that supply should always be maintained at its optimal level of buffer stock. This collaboration shall lead to an innovative measure to strengthen the community’s awareness of the problem regarding insufficient warehouse logistics, thereby would lead to innovative efforts such as, but not limited to, active community participation and empowerment. This study concludes that a proactive approach of orientation coupled with a positive advocacy drive can achieve collaborative governance and synergies among the stakeholders to face the challenges in the public sector. It is very important to recognize and include the different values and perspectives of the multi-stakeholders to be able for them to appreciate the significance of the project and policy guidelines being implemented. Collaboration in this project has been touted as a valuable tool of innovation. Community partnering can develop and establish development opportunities. The government as a backbone of the society could not do it alone, the participation of the community is very critical to materialize an impact project. However, embracing collaborative governance acknowledges that it is no easy. There are always impediments to fulfilling it, hence, it is a challenge to build a more compassionate atmosphere. Being more persistent in advocating this mechanism is the central factor to attain a collaborative environment.

Keywords: *national food authority, community partnering, ensured food security logistics*

Introduction

Rice is a highly political commodity as it is the main staple of the country. It has always been at the forefront of agricultural policies in government. Most of the strategies focus on fostering food self-sufficiency, providing rice farmers with high incomes, and making prices affordable to consumers (Tobias, Molina, Valera, Mottaleb, and Mohanty, 2012).

One of the biggest shifts in the agricultural sector was when President Rodrigo R. Duterte signed the Rice Tariffication Law (RTL) titled “An Act liberalizing the importation, exportation, and trading of rice, lifting for the purpose the quantitative import restriction on rice, and for other purposes” last February 14, 2019. This is also known as the Rice Liberalization Act or Republic Act No. 11203, which amends the Agricultural Tariffication Act of 1996 that imposed tariffs on agricultural imports except for rice (Dansal, 2019).

Most of the economic managers believe that rice liberalization through the overflowing of rice from the exporting countries is an effective mechanism to have cheaper rice in the market. With the implementation of the foregoing law, local farmers have been seen as the major affected sector. About 32% of the land is dedicated to agriculture. Likewise, 26% of Filipino workers cultivate lands or farmers (PSA, 2014)

Villamar (2017) articulated that in times that the market price of palay is volatile, the government intervenes through the National Food Authority (NFA) to ensure the fair return of their labors NFA is a government instrumentality and is vested to ensure food security of the country. The food agency procurement program supports farmers' market mechanisms as market price and government support price is clearly associated.

Occidental Mindoro is one of the rice granaries not only in the Southern Tagalog Region but also in the whole country as seen in the report of PSA. In NFA’s perspective, the coverage of jurisdiction of the Provincial Office is under the category of “surplus” area in terms of palay production. In the Market Situation Report 2020 (MSR) of the branch, the daily consumption requirement is 2,780 bags

in rice form or 41,700 bags in compliance with 15-day buffer stocks, but the produced is much more than enough.

With this, NFA in general holds the challenge on how to attain the mandated buffer stock level as dictated by the tariffication law. Hence, it is a source of buffer stocks for the highly dependent areas, both mainland and island provinces not only in the Southern Tagalog Region but also in other regions. NFA rice is tactically placed to ensure that it is available, accessible, affordable, and safe at any given time especially in times of emergencies and calamities.

Given the above situation, the NFA management, after having established a 2020 palay procurement target of 2,705,000 bags for the branch, has set a target that corresponds to 18% and 48% of the national and regional targets, respectively (Grains Marketing Plan 2020). The monetary value of the predetermined target amounted to almost three (3) billion pesos for palay purchases only, excluding other operating expenses like trucking/hauling, handling, security services, general services, pest control, sacks, pallets, warehouses rental, personnel services, and other maintenance & operating expenses.

Further, in order to ensure that our local farmers are able to cope with the competition among the commercial imported rice as stipulated in the liberalization act on rice as a primary commodity, NFA was given the function to ensure that farmers' produce is still well accommodated as buffer stocks during emergencies and disasters.

As NFA Occidental Mindoro Provincial Office was hailed as the Top Performer among branches all over the Philippines in palay procurement operation of the agency in 2019, a substantial part of its national target was given to the branch. Green, Whitten, and Inman (2008) affirmed that there is a constructive relationship between logistics performance and organizational performance.

Therefore, the readiness of logistics in terms of storage warehousing of the produce would help to achieve the success of the agency. It shall contribute to the attainment of the predetermined targets of the marketing operations. Quigley & Robertson (2015) emphasized that the storage capacity is one of the most important logistics required for palay procurement operation. This is to ensure that stored stocks are maintained in good and consumable condition.

The NFA's powers and functions in rice importation, as well as the other regulatory functions in the local grains industry such as registration, licensing, and supervision of persons/entities engaged in the rice and corn businesses to generate industry information necessary for policy and decision-making, enforcement of rice trading rules and regulations, regulation of rice importation and exportation, and importation of rice for national food security buffer stocking are now repealed due to approval of Rice Tariffication Law.

Today, the main function of the NFA is solely to maintain sufficient rice buffer stock to be sourced solely from local farmers (R.A. 11203). It denotes that the agency will continue to be the custodian of government buffer stocks to respond to the need for immediate distribution of rice during calamities and emergencies anywhere across the country.

Research Objectives

The main challenge that this capstone project would like to address was the difficulties confronted by NFA as it struggles to find enough storage logistics in the areas during the procurement period season. Specifically, this study was able to answer the following mechanisms to address the identified difficulty confronted by the NFA:

1. Identified the different measures currently being utilized by the NFA to respond to the insufficiency of storage logistics to house the buffer stocks of palay.
2. Recognized possible collaborations between the NFA and the community to safeguard the volume of production by local farmers.
3. Articulated interventions and innovations from both private and government as part of the proposed Action Plan and Program (APP).

The researcher was also able to achieve the purpose of this capstone project.

1. Forged an official agreement with the LGUs of SAMARICA, Occidental Mindoro through its community leaders to pilot a Community Collaborative Plan for Buffer Stock Storage with the specific barangays under study.
2. Crafted guidelines on good warehouse keeping and quality management for the adoption of the partner communities.
3. Conducted orientation activities targeted for the NFA staff and the community stakeholders and leaders.

Due to current situations, the development and implementation of the Community Collaborative Plan for Buffer Stock Storage as well as the monitoring of feedback were formed part of the sustainability plan.

As mentioned in Villamar (2017), former NFA Administrator Renan B. Dalisay highlighted that the government, in intensifying the palay procurement, is like hitting two birds with one stone because it helps us build up the country's buffer stock of rice, which we will need during the lean season or if incoming typhoons damaged rice crop and at the same time, it allows us to help local farmers, who should be encouraged to plant rice – our nation's staple food as they (farmers) deserve to earn more for their hard work.

To provide a clearer notion of the challenge addressed by this project is the figure shown below:

Figure 1: Causal Loop

This research work focused its attention to one of the significant functions of NFA as highlighted in the 2020 Strategy Map, and that is ensuring that there is enough rice for the people and that their supply always maintained the optimal level of buffer stock through local palay procurement and ensures it is strategically located across the country.

The table below shows the NFA Market Participation in Palay Procurement for the past four decades:

Table 1. NFA's Absorption Rate

Year	Average Actual Procurement	Average Palay Production	% of Absorption
1980-1989	776,602	2,820,669	27.53%
1990-1999	530,997	3,047,668	17.42%
2000-2009	1,140,943	3,256,930	35.03%
2010-2019	1,078,068	4,266,949	25.27%

**Historical Data of the NFA Occidental Mindoro Provincial Office*

Based on the above-presented table, it illustrates that the highest government participation of 35.03% in terms of palay procurement was in the year 2000-2009, followed by years 1980-1989 and 2010-2019 with 27.53% and 25.27% absorption rate, respectively. Slightly low participation by 17.42% in 1990-1999.

NFA sets procurement target from Central Office down to Regional office considering various factors such as but not limited to Inventory on hand at the end of the year, Volume of Production, Daily Consumption Rate, Space Logistics, and Minimum Level of Buffer Stocks. The Regional Office allocates a predetermined target to the Provincial Offices.

Table 2 demonstrates the accomplishment of NFA Occidental Mindoro in terms of palay procurement.

Table 2. Procurement Operation Accomplishment

Year	Actual Procurement	Target	% of Accomplishment
2010	2,002,216	1,909,965	104.83%
2011	1,359,817	1,719,981	79.06%
2012	1,466,827	1,565,785	93.68%
2013	1,207,490	1,379,989	87.50%
2014	145,660	789,913	18.44%
2015	1,317,021	1,315,048	100.15%
2016	892,412	949,981	93.94%
2017	177,539	889,920	19.95%
2018	595,158	891,088	66.79%
2019	1,616,541	1,923,995	84.02%
Average	1,078,068	1,333,567	80.84%

**Historical Data of the NFA Occidental Mindoro Provincial Office*

It was established from the gathered data that for the past ten years, there were only two years that the branch exceeded the set target – 2010 and 2015 (104.83% and 100.15%, respectively). It can be assessed that one of the contributing factors to non-attainment of the set targets would practically be attributed to the scarcity of resources in the area particularly the warehousing logistic.

Notwithstanding the branch's achievement, NFA has continuously faced numerous challenges, especially in storage capacity in the last three decades. To accommodate the needs of the farmers, NFA provisionally adopted the "Outside Piling" strategy within the vicinity of the warehouses. However, this approach led to high risk on the part of Stock Accountable Officers (SAOs), quality of the grains, and the agency itself.

Based on the warehouse library of the branch, the statistics below evidently display that there is insufficiency in the storage logistic of NFA Occidental Mindoro. The capacity is a significant characteristic of a facility. The constraints in storage limit the total workload for which the facility will be responsible (Battini, 2008).

Table 3. *Warehouse Capacity Analysis*

<i>Municipality</i>	<i>Existing Warehouse Capacity (bags)</i>	<i>Total Grains for Storage (bags)</i>	<i>Surplus/ (Deficit) (bags)</i>
San Jose	694,817	2,705,000	(1,809,588)
Magsaysay	11,048		
Rizal	77,451		
Calintaan	112,096		
TOTAL	895,412		

**Status of Warehouse Utilization Report 2019*

The gathered data established a gap with a significant volume of more than 1.8 million bags. It also reveals that 77% of the total capacity can be found in San Jose Area (sole 1st class municipality among the four), where the Main Office is located. Depending on the geographical area of the market, the institution needs to have a network of warehouses considering the location and capacity of the warehouse (Murthy & Blischke, 2006). In a further study of Lovgren and Orrskog (2012), they affirmed that successful warehousing maximizes the effective utilization of the warehouse resources while satisfying customer requirements.

According to Administrator Dansal, NFA will never realize a profit and maintain financial stability as required by RA 11203 for as long it is tasked to render service at a loss. In actuality, the rule of thumb in rice marketing is to double the price of palay when sold at rice to make a profit. But then, the government has a social responsibility to ensure food security – even at a loss (Olarde, 2016). The agency formulated devises productivity guidelines to improve and maintain a sustainable amount of buffer stock that would ensure that there is enough food for everyone.

This capstone project at a glance could be seen as simple and fundamental, yet the proponent has positively foreseen high impact and innovative outcomes. At the end of the day, it is hoped that the benefits will be directed to the individual farmers and the farmers' groups/organizations/associations/cooperatives because NFA will be able to procure their produce.

Methodology

Research Design

Basically, the nature of this study was an action research design. The method of study applied was to seek a solution to the problem in storage capacity faced by the NFA. The branch has limited space capacity to accommodate the million bags of palay deliveries by the individual farmers and the farmers' organizations/ groups/ cooperatives/ associations. This was a social research joined by different levels of the government and the selected communities. Thus, the NFA tried to seek assistance from the local government units as well as from the community to enhance the space logistics of the agency. The broad involvement of the multi-stakeholders promoted a just and participatory change.

The study also utilized the descriptive-narrative method with a questionnaire as the data gathering tool supplemented by personal interviews, forums, and focus group discussion. Descriptive-survey research used surveys to gather data about varying subjects. This data aimed to know the extent to which different conditions can be obtained among these subjects (Anonymous, 2020). The following approaches were undertaken to achieve the possible solutions to the identified problems, which were the tangible outputs of the capstone project:

- Forged MOA on collaboration with Local Government Units
- Proposed action plan for the sustainability of the project
- Crafted guidelines for logistic warehouse maintenance

Participants

The research site of the study was the SAMARICA Area, one of the two legislative districts in Occidental Mindoro. The 2nd district, composed of municipalities of San Jose, Magsaysay, Rizal, and Calintaan. The said district is the entire coverage area or jurisdiction of the NFA Occidental Mindoro Provincial Office.

The units of the study were the public officials from Municipal Local Government Units (MLGUs) and Barangay Local Government Units (BLGUs) of San Jose, Magsaysay, Rizal, and Calintaan, Occidental Mindoro. We also requested information from the Municipal Agriculturist Offices (MAOs).

The officers of the Provincial Farmers Association Council (PFAC) as well as the four Municipal Farmers Association Council (MFACs) were participants of this research. Included in the contributors were the business sectors that were engaged in agriculture particularly in palay farming.

The project team members, the management, and the staff of NFA Occidental Mindoro were also the key informants of the project.

Procedure

In order to accomplish the substantial data in crafting the needed information and statistics that would put credibility to the concretizing of collaborative governance program between NFA and the community, the data gathering processes employed were the following:

- Requested permission addressed to the Provincial Manager to seek authorization to conduct a study and request for data and information.
- Invited farmers' leaders for focus group discussions.
- Letter requests were forwarded to the identified local government units to make a schedule for consultative meetings and advocacy campaigns. After which, inquiry on which units have existing storage facilities such as multi-purpose hall in their respective jurisdiction.
- To determine the volume of production per municipality and per barangay, letter of requests were presented to the Municipal Agriculturist Offices followed by meetings and consultation to validate and expound the gathered information.

Data Analysis

This study used both qualitative and quantitative data collection tools. The qualitative tools of analysis employed was the one-on-one discussion or in-depth interviews to deepen the understanding of the problem. It also used focus group discussion to get the perceptions and insights of the farmers concerning the issue of insufficient storage capacity.

This capstone project's initial aim was to first complete the significant data in establishing the needed information and statistics that would put credence to the concretizing of collaborative governance program between NFA and the community. The information gathered through a quantitative approach was summarized and analyzed using Microsoft Excel.

Figure 1. *Framework Analysis*

Phase 1 included the planning of the capstone project to define the objective, scope, coverage, and roadmap. The constitution of the team members, the securing of permits to conduct the study, and the orientation of the capstone team were part of this stage. Phase 2 involved data gathering from both internal and external parties to give credence to the study. The team also undertook an identification process of the possible local government units. Phase 3 referred to the implementation of the capstone project. The key activities encompass were focus group discussion and advocacy campaign with the farmers, as well as consultative meetings and negotiations with the local officials. Phase 4 entailed the final and tangible output of the study. The last part comprised summarizing, analyzing, evaluating, and assessing the key activities undertaken to come up with the MOA on Collaboration, Guidelines on Logistics Warehouse Maintenance, and Sustainability Plan.

Implementation Plan and Process

Table 4. *Implementation Plan*

<i>Objective</i>	<i>Major Activity</i>	<i>Result and Success Indicator</i>	<i>Person/ Group Responsible</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Risks (Potential, Obstacle, Constraints)</i>	<i>Risks Treatment (Preventive, Contingency Action)</i>	<i>Budget</i>
Preparatory Stage							
	Coordinate with the Provincial Management	Attendance of the meeting	Provincial Management	3 rd week of August 2020	Conflict of schedules	Reschedule the meeting	P0.00
	Create the Capstone Project Team	Office Order on the composition of the CP Team	Provincial Management, Project Proponent	3 rd week of August 2020	Unavailability of the persons involved	Consultation and Conference with Provincial Management	P0.00
	Orient the Capstone Project Team	Attendance of the Orientation	PM, Proponent, and CP Team	4 th week of August 2020	Unavailability of the persons involved	Schedule ahead of time	P500.00
To promote support for the implementation of the CP	Ask permission to gather internal information	Timeliness and completeness of the requested information	Planning and Statistics Section, Marketing Operations Section	1 st week of Sep 2020	Absence of the needed information	Provide timetable on the submission of the reports	P0.00
IMPLEMENTATION							
To gather data on the volume of production	Coordinate with Municipal Agriculturists	Attendance of coordination	CP Team MAOs	2 nd week of Sep 2020	Unavailability of the persons involved Transportation logistics	Time to time coordination Advance request of service vehicle	P1,000.00
To request support from the local farmers	Focus Group Discussion with the local farmers	Attendance of the FGD Minutes of the FGD	Provincial Farmers Action Council (PFAC) Municipal Farmers Action Council (MFAC) CP Team	2 nd week of Sep 2020	Conflict of Schedules FGD is conducted through face to face	Reschedule the FGD Strictly observe the physical distancing and other health and safety protocol	P2,000.00
To craft guidelines on logistic warehouse maintenance	Refresher course on Quality Management	Results of the Refresher course	Technical Research and Standard Department CP Team	2 nd week of Sep 2020	Conflict of Schedules Refresher course is conducted through face to face	Office memo on the conduct of the activity Strictly observe the physical distancing and other health and safety protocol	P3,000.00
To conduct advocacy campaign, consultation, and negotiation	Consultative meetings with identified LGUs	Minutes of the meetings	Local Community Leaders and NFA Staff	Oct to Nov 2020	Unavailability of Personnel involved	Reschedule the meeting	P5,000.00
	Compose Memorandum of Agreement	Draft of MOA	Local Community Leaders and NFA Staff	Nov 2020	Unclear Stipulations on Agreement	Review and Calibration	P2,000.00
POST IMPLEMENTATION							
To forge an official agreement with the LGU of Occidental Mindoro	Signing of MOA	Signed MOAs	Local Community Leaders and NFA Management	Nov 2020	Conflict of Schedules	Set specific schedules	P 3000.00
To finalize the Capstone Project	Write the Capstone Final Report	Capstone Final Report	Project Proponent, FA, IP, Panel	Dec 2020	Unavailability of Personnel involved Poor Internet Connectivity	Conference with FA & IP	P5000.00
	Capstone Report Final Presentation to the Panel	Evaluation of Capstone Final Presentation	Project Proponent, FA, IP, Panel	Dec 2020	Unavailability of Personnel involved	Reschedule of Final Presentation	

Prepare Final Manuscript, Collateral and Other Resources	Written Final Manuscript	Project Proponent, FA, IP, Panel	Dec 2020	Poor Internet Connectivity Unavailability of Personnel involved Poor Internet Connectivity	Conference with FA & IP Use of Mobile Connection
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Results and Discussion

Detailed Account of the Intervention

It had been the intention of this capstone project to investigate how the National Food Authority – Occidental Mindoro Provincial Office was able to respond to an identified problem regarding the insufficiency of storage logistics to house the buffer stock of palay during procurement season in Occidental Mindoro. This perennial problem has already been an on-going issue of the NFA since time immemorial. In fact, its recurrence every year has prompted the agency to take measures to make sure that there will be enough storage and warehouse areas for the palay, which this capstone sought to address. This capstone project was divided into three phases: Preparatory, Implementation, and Post Implementation

Further, the collaboration between the National Food Authority and the community were also taken into consideration along with the conduct of this study. This hoped to help the agency to plan actions and activities that would further enhance the relationship between the two entities in providing safety measures covering the volume of production of palay by local farmers.

Accordingly, this capstone project also provided some suggestions on what particular interventions and innovations can be solicited both from private and government as part of the proposed Action Plan and Program (APP).

Preparatory Stage

In order to find answers to problem number one, the proponent was able to extract information from their data files, while other information were taken from one-on one interviews with the NFA officials who handled marketing operations.

During the initial stages of the study, the proponent coordinated with the officials of the NFA for support; and asked permission to conduct the data gathering acting as a representative of the agency. After explaining the objectives and getting the approval, the Capstone Project Team (CPT) was constituted through Office Order OCM-2020-H-52 dated August 20, 2020. The members were cautiously chosen based on their abilities to articulate their opinions and technical knowledge as reflected in their previous performance evaluations and assessments. Additionally, their willingness and commitment were also important considerations in choosing them as part of the CPT.

The Office Order was posted on the Bulletin Board of the Provincial Office, sent to the group chat of the employees, and forwarded to the NFA Southern Tagalog Region for information dissemination. A messenger group chat was also created, which was exclusively for the capstone team in order to facilitate easy access to information and efficient communication.

To appreciate more about the significance of the capstone project, the researcher initiated the capstone project orientation to the members of the team on August 25, 2020. He discussed the definition of the capstone, its characteristics, the possible thematic areas, the capstone project phases, and the development plans. Further, it was also on the same day where the capstone project was launched. The researcher presented the approved capstone project proposal for the implementation in the NFA Occidental Mindoro Provincial Office. The major activities, timeline, needed resources, and responsible persons for each of the activities, were reviewed and evaluated by the team.

The Provincial Management spearheaded by Provincial Manager Roberto C. Gonzales and Assistant Provincial Manager Evelyn P. Sy, during the orientation emphasized the importance of everyone’s cooperation and participation, particularly on their assigned tasks to help the Capstone Project materialize positively.

In order for the proponent to gain access to the information that he needed for this capstone; he requested the management to give him the permission to request for the data files that would specifically answer the problems at hand.

During this process, the proponent was able to secure the following information that would answer to the different measures currently being utilized by the NFA to respond to the identified problem on the insufficiency of the storage logistic to house the palay.

There were seven NFA owned warehouses which majority had their sites in the San Jose, Occidental Mindoro, the same place where the main Provincial Office of the branch is located. The terminal warehouses had cumulative effective capacity of 442,800 if stocked with palay, while 492,000 if stocked with rice.

Table 5. *NFA Owned Warehouses*

Warehouse	Location	Rated Capacity		Effective Capacity	
		In Palay	In Rice	In Palay	In Rice
GID I	San Jose, OM	50,000	50,000	45,000	50,000
GID II	San Jose, OM	50,000	50,000	45,000	50,000
GID III	Calintaan, OM	100,000	100,000	90,000	100,000
GID IV	San Jose, OM	100,000	100,000	90,000	100,000
GID V	San Jose, OM	100,000	100,000	90,000	100,000
Nawaco I	San Jose, OM	30,000	30,000	27,000	30,000
Nawaco II	San Jose, OM	62,000	62,000	55,800	62,000

Aside from NFA warehouses, the agency also invited warehousing business entities to engage with the NFA by leasing their warehouses. Based on the warehouse library as of February 2020, the leased warehouses/buying stations of the branch were as follows:

Table 6. *Leased Warehouses*

Warehouse	Location	Rated Capacity		Effective Capacity	
		In Palay	In Rice	In Palay	In Rice
JAFPY	San Jose, OM	119,448	143,338	95,558	114,670
PACUNLA 1	San Jose, OM	25,830	30,996	20,664	24,797
PACUNLA 2	San Jose, OM	26,000	54,000	28,800	43,200
PACUNLA 3	San Jose, OM	45,360	54,432	36,288	43,546
RONQUILLO	San Jose, OM	84,416	101,299	67,533	81,040
ALMUETE	San Jose, OM	43,200	51,840	34,560	41,472
ALMUETE 2	San Jose, OM	16,800	25,200	13,440	20,160
BALMADRID	San Jose, OM	45,000	54,000	24,000	36,000
SABADECO	San Jose, OM	21,840	18,200	14,560	17,472
SEBASTIAN	San Jose, OM	42,640	51,168	33,944	40,934
CAJETA	San Jose, OM	48,000	72,000	38,400	57,600
L'SQUARE	Rizal, OM	21,600	25,920	17,280	20,736
TAGUMPAY	Rizal, OM	7,200	8,640	5,760	6,912
PAKIKIBAGAI	Rizal, OM	8,061	9,674	6,449	7,739
SALVACION	Rizal, OM	8,123	9,747	6,498	7,798
MAMAMUCO	Rizal, OM	11,340	13,608	9,072	10,886
CONDE	Rizal, OM	14,625	17,550	11,700	14,040
PABLO	Rizal, OM	28,560	34,271	22,848	27,417
PECHON	Rizal, OM	8,550	12,825	6,840	9,619
SALINDONG	Rizal, OM	10,560	15,840	8,448	12,672
JAURIGE	Rizal, OM	25,880	31,056	20,704	24,845
MILLER	Rizal, OM	16,200	19,440	10,368	15,552
NEW DAGUPAN	Calintaan, OM	15,120	18,144	12,096	14,515
NEW LIFE	Calintaan, OM	10,535	12,642	8,428	10,114
MFCFMPC	Calintaan, OM	6,460	7,752	5,168	6,202
MAGSAYSAY ORIG	Magsaysay, OM	7,350	8,820	5,880	7,056
GAMOT FA	Magsaysay, OM	3,840	4,608	3,072	3,686

The warehouse rentals were based on the strategic locations yet still subjected to facility management assessment. There was a time that the farmers clamored for the agency to accommodate all their harvest because there had been lack of storage space. Hence, the management came-up with the decision to maximize the vicinity of the warehouse and temporarily devise a so called “outside piling”.

Another strategy was that NFA made sure to conduct “Farmers’ Ugnayan”- an assembly meeting of NFA with the community stakeholders where they discuss concerns that had something to do with the procurement process (before and during the onset of the harvest seasons).

The management also coordinated with the rice millers to process palay. This operation was another contingent measure of the agency to create space. Extensive rice domestic exports to highly dependent areas were also seen as strategies.

NFA came up with aggressive sales strategies among government institutions, relief operations agencies, accredited retailers, and other interested private institutions to make sure that there will be movements of rice and leave better space for other stocks.

Implementation Stage

The data gathering of the team started by visiting the Offices of the Municipal Agriculturist in San Jose, Magsaysay, Rizal, and Calintaan (SaMaRiCa, Occidental Mindoro) to identify the volume of production for the last three years per barangay in their area of jurisdiction. This was to ascertain which barangays had voluminous palay production. The gathered information was tallied to compare with the set target in the marketing plan and analyzed to know the absorption rate of the agency.

The invitation letters were sent to farmers' leaders for a focus group discussion. The primary purpose of the FGD is to solicit ideas from the farmers to come up with a sustainable collaborative program. Leaders from the Provincial Farmers Action Council (PFAC) and Municipal Farmers Action Council (MFAC) were present for the discussion. The team was able to orient on the purpose of the Capstone Project.

Inspired by the results of doing focus group discussion with the farmers-leaders, they scheduled several meetings with the community stakeholders especially the Local Government Units in order to explain the objectives of the capstone.

During the meetings and after identifying the essentials of common issues regarding the proper stocking of palay, his first deliverable was to check on the capabilities of the LGUs in the provision of warehouses for the farmers for proper palay stocking during harvest time. In the process, it was found out that there was still a need for more improvements in the logistics of keeping the warehouses safe and worthy for use, especially during typhoons and other natural calamities. This prompted him to give way to the first objective and the first deliverable of the capstone which is the "crafting of guidelines (Appendix A) on good warehouse maintenance and quality management for the adoption of the agency and the partner communities.

The team asked the assistance from the Technical Research and Standard Department (TRSD) in formulating the warehouse maintenance guidelines. There have been a number of outcomes that were considered to be highly significant in coming up with guidelines and policies which will assist NFA and the community stakeholders in resolving the issues that were identified.

One of the by-products of this activity was the drafting of guidelines and procedures for properly maintaining the storage logistics that has been regarded as a long-running problem among the farmers during procurement time. Accordingly, NFA also saw this as a challenge in carrying out their duties and responsibilities as the government agency to oversee the process of buffer stocking.

The idea of doing updated quality assurance policies and guidelines on the implementation and adoption of good warehouse-keeping were also identified to be a top priority of interest among the participants.

Finally, the group also was able to illustrate the appropriate measurement of dimension and standard of storage systems. During the process of discussion, the participants had highly shown significant technical knowledge in carrying out their tasks which became a good sign of efficiency and effective work performances.

During the process of gathering information, the team was able to introduce the Capstone Project, its significance, and purpose to the Municipal Agricultural and Fisheries Council (MAFC) Forum of Calintaan, Occidental Mindoro, though they were not part of the itinerary of the proponent. The opportunity was taken last September 19, 2020 as part of his groundworks in penetrating various communities,

After which, a series of consultative meetings with the different barangays of San Jose (Magbay and Central) were carried out as part of the scheduled activities for this Capstone Project.

The BLGU of Magbay acknowledged the efforts of the team and considered supporting the project after the presentation of the draft of the MOA between the NFA and their end. The meeting was done last October 5, 2020.

However, the Consultative Meeting with MLGU of San Jose did not push through last October 5 because of a sudden surge in the number of COVID cases in the municipality. Again, the re-schedules of meetings later (October 28) were also canceled due to bad weather - series of typhoons (Quinta and Rolly).

Another consultative meeting with the Barangay Council of Tanyag, Calintaan last October 7. Luckily, the team was able to present the Capstone Project and the deliverables.

The BLGU of Tanyag acknowledged the efforts of the team and considered supporting the project after the presentation of the draft of MOA between the NFA and their end. With the drafting of MOA last October 17 and October 24, by the Capstone Project Team (CPT), they were able to accomplish the following:

- Transcribe the audio recordings of consultative meetings.
- Classify and organize the understanding of concepts, observations, considerations, and visions of participants in the forum.
- Draft the content of the MOA on Collaboration.

Surprisingly, although it had not been part of the implementation plan, the team got another chance to introduce the significance of the Capstone Project during the forum of Municipal Agricultural and Fisheries Council (MAFC) – Magsaysay last October 22, 2020.

Again, the scheduled consultative meetings with MLGU of Rizal (October 26), MLGU of Calintaan (October 27), and MLGU of Magsaysay (October 29) did not push through due to the series of typhoons (Quinta and Rolly). Aside from these, the scheduling of meetings became doubly difficult due to the unavailability of public officials due to more pressing local concerns.

While the requests to the above mention MLGUs were still pending for consideration, the proponent constantly consulted his Faculty Adviser and Institutional Partner and discussed the content of the drafted MOA on Collaboration. All their suggestions and recommendations were considered and incorporated. Simultaneously, the drafted MOA on Collaboration was also distributed to the

Provincial Management for their insights and the same was also integrated for the betterment of the MOA.

The CPT was able to present the capstone project to the BLGU of Salvacion, Rizal on November 10, 2020. During the meeting, they were informed of the deliverables of the project. Hence, on the November 24 barangay session of BLGU Salvacion, the team encouraged the council to allow their barangay captain to enter MOA on Collaboration with NFA. The said proposal was approved by the council on the same day.

After a month of waiting for the consideration of MLGUs, the team finally got schedules with the mayors of MLGU of Magsaysay and Rizal on November 24 and 26, respectively. After presenting the objectives and deliverable of the Capstone Project, it was endorsed to Sangguniang Bayan for the authority of the mayor to enter MOA.

Even weekend, the proponent personally visited the barangay captain of BLGU of Central, San Jose, and had a one-on-one discussion of the capstone project on November 29, 2020. He invited the proponent to attend the next barangay session (December 1, 2020) to discuss the project with the council and solicit their support. Without objection, the council has approved the recommendation that their barangay captain would enter into MOA on Collaboration with NFA.

The CPT and the Provincial Management conducted the final review of the MOA on Collaboration. After it was concluded, the team deliver MOAs to the identified BLGUs and MLGUs for their reviews and comments.

Post-Implementation

After having conducted such meetings, the next in the process of deliverables was to forge a Memorandum of Agreement with the identified LGUs of Occidental Mindoro. Although the main targets of this study were the BLGUs, during the process, the proponent was also able to close an agreement with the municipal government which stipulated the same agreement with the barangays.

As a gesture of support, the Municipal Government of Magsaysay represented by Mayor Cesar M. Tria, Jr. signed MOA on Collaboration on December 2, 2020. Due to his busy schedules caused by local pressing issues, he requested not to have a MOA Signing Ceremony.

On December 11, 2020, the Provincial Management together with the CPT traveled to three different towns to conduct MOA on Collaboration Ceremony. The following are BLGUs that showed support to the project:

- BLGU of Tanyag in Calintaan, Occidental Mindoro represented by Barangay Captain Reden T. Perez,
- BLGU of Salvacion in Rizal, Occidental Mindoro represented by Barangay Captain Danilo C. Soriano, and
- BLGU of Central in San Jose, Occidental Mindoro represented by Barangay Captain Orlando T. Losauro

The ceremonial activities were successful and fruitful because aside from the intended activity, the Provincial Management was able to relay the new thrust of the agency.

Because of the full schedules of Barangay Captain Nestor J. Salongsongan from BLGU of Magbay in San Jose Occidental Mindoro, the supposed schedule was move to December 22, 2020. Also, there is pending approval of Sangguniang Bayan of Rizal, Occidental Mindoro to allow Mayor Ernesto C. Pablo, Jr to enter into a MOA in collaboration with NFA.

Considering all the community consultations (focus group discussion, one-on-one dialogue, forums, and refresher course) to come up with the deliverables such as crafting of guidelines on warehouse maintenance, and signing of MOA on Collaboration, both NFA and the community had to make sure that those responsibilities set by the MOA, which was to be duly accomplished by them, should be in operation and place.

Actual Deliverables versus Expected Deliverables

This capstone project has three deliverables after the implementation: MOA on Collaboration with LGU, Guidelines for Logistics Warehouse Maintenance, and Action Plan for the Sustainability of the Project. All these deliverables were achieved and implemented by the NFA and the Community Partners.

MOA on Collaboration

On the second questions on what possible collaborations between the NFA and he communities were being taken to safeguard the volume of production by local farmers, the proponent made the necessary linkages with the Local Government Units, starting from the level of the barangay, to make grassroots research on how the farmers were looking at this problem. From there, the proponent made an initiative to propose to the National Food Authority and the local communities to come-up with a coordinated project that would help the community draw an alternative ground for the proper warehouse storage.

The data gathered were done through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with the farmers and other community stakeholders. Prior to that, the proponent discussed with the NFA provincial management the rationale of this project and how it could help both the NFA and the community regarding issues during procurement season. Upon consultations with both groups, it showed that one of the major problems confronting both NFA and the farmers was that of the storage logistics. Using the results of these consultations, the researcher

pushed for more in-depth interviews with the local government units or barangay councils to validate the results of the first consultative meetings.

Following this line of thought, the proponent was able to come up with an output in the form of an Action Plan and Program (APP) that directly dealt with the results of the coordination and collaboration of the NFA and the community regarding how storage areas can be maximized in the community setting.

There were four Barangay Local Government Units namely Tanyag, Salvacion, Central, and Magbay who signified their commitment to collaborate with the NFA through sealing of MOA on Collaboration. The parties agreed to the following agreement:

NFA shall:

- Spearhead the implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of the project;
- Shoulder the logistical and incidental expenses which may be incurred in the implementation of the project;
- Constitute a technical working group for the purposes related to and relevant to the project;
- Coordinate with the BLGU in matters arising from the project; and
- Prepare the necessary progress and terminal reports and furnish the barangay with a copy of the same.

LGU shall:

- Allow NFA to utilize the BLGU infrastructure as procurement and storage facilities for local produce;
- Spearhead an economic development campaign and forge public-private partnerships to encourage interested parties to engage in warehousing business;
- Seek to establish a multipurpose facility in the Barangay;
- Encourage farmers' cooperatives, groups, and associations to build a storage facility; and
- Assist the NFA to secure a land donation to be utilized in building a storage facility.

Given the situation that we are confronting nowadays, the primary targets of this study were BLGUs. However, the team was able to present with the MLGUs. They were encouraged to be a partner in this kind of impact project. Hence, after a consultative meeting with MLGU Magsaysay, they signified their intention to collaborate through the sealing of MOA. The request for the authority of the Mayor of Rizal to enter MOA was still pending and was subjected to the reading in Sangguniang Bayan Session. Thus, the target number of actual deliverables exceeded the expected number of deliverables in terms of the forging of MOAs.

Guidelines for Logistics Warehouse Maintenance

In order to ensure the quality of government buffer stocking, the standards for warehouse logistics were crafted. The guidelines served as a basis for the warehouse personnel to safeguard the inventory that was strategically positioned and maintained by the National Food Authority at any given time especially for emergency situations and for government disaster relief operations that are sufficient, quality, and safe. This directive was for the guidance and consumption of both internal and external stakeholders of the NFA.

The Memorandum Circular No: OCM-L-2020-81 dated December 1, 2020 was posted on the bulletin board of the Provincial Office and all warehouses (NFA Owned and Leased). It was also distributed to all LGU partners. Incorporated in the general provision of the guidelines were the proximity/site location. This is where the warehouses should be accessible.

Another common consideration was the security assessment of the area. The jurisdiction should maintain peace and order to ensure the safety of the public property. During the consultative meetings, safety measures of the government assets were discussed. It was very important to have active community support for addressing the internal and external issues and challenges such as but not limited to the following: law, order, and administration of justice, internal armed conflicts, terrorism, and transnational crime, economic and social threats.

The specific policies and provisions of the guidelines focused on technical specifications like building structure, warehouse ventilation, the characters of flooring and drainage as well as the lightings. The methods to maintain warehouse hygiene and sanitation were also identified. Ultimately, the stockpiling system which was very crucial in warehouse maintenance, were considered to prevent any spillage of grains and from the possibility of the piles to collapse.

Action Plan for the Sustainability of the Project

This capstone goes back to the identification of the inputs that were needed to understand the coverage of the research. These inputs were those that were identified as the NFA Storage Logistics and which was the central variables used to determine the types of storage that were being utilized by the farmers during procurement time.

These storages were primarily identified to be a problem among NFA and the community stakeholders. In which case, this study tried to focus its concern on how to resolve the issue especially at this time when an oversupply of palay becomes an eventuality due to the implementation of the Rice Tariffication Law (RA11203). The proponent is an employee and whose concern was towards the improvement of internal and external processes and in order to come up with significant information that would help materialize the

proper operational procedures.

This APP shall be comprehensively discussed and put into order at the latter part of this capstone recommendations. After which, NFA has taken responsibility for the monitoring and collection of feedbacks from various segments of the community which will include the internal and external stakeholders of NFA. These feedbacks shall be utilized to make further improvements to future action planning of programs for the community.

Deviations from the Original Plan

Generally, the objectives of this Capstone Project were accomplished considering the challenges it had encountered. There are some minor deviations during the implementation, but these changes contribute to the achievement of the deliverables. Although the main participants of this project were the BLGUs in consideration of our current situations, the team was able to introduce the significance of the Capstone Project and seal MOA on Collaboration with MLGU.

The changes in the calendar of activities were the usual deviations that are being encountered by researchers. Due to local urgent issues needed to be addressed, hence, there were scheduled consultative meetings that were postponed.

Aside from time constraints, there were added methods of implementation. Other than formal consultative meetings and focus group discussions, the team was able to attend two forums and presented the Capstone Project. The informal one-on-one dialogue was also utilized by the proponent to lobby support.

Identified Challenges and Resolutions

The whole process was not without difficulties or challenges. In fact, right from the start, it was like finding a needle in a stack of hay. The proponent being an employee of the NFA was confronted with the possibility that he may come up with an issue that cannot be even be resolved; or a problem which solution is still beyond recognition, especially at this time of the pandemic.

One of the challenges that the proponent has to face was the restriction of a face-to-face interview with the community. The representations of the respondents may also have been too constrained because not everyone could come for a consultation due to health protocols. There was a time that the schedule of consultative meeting to one of the municipalities in SAMARICA district was postponed and has not materialized because all employees were subjected to a swab test and the municipal government had been temporarily closed for two weeks.

Another challenge was the possibility of not getting the correct information from the respondents for fear that there might be some financial or logistical counterparts that would be solicited from them, and which at that point, they were not able to offer due to limited budgets of the local government.

It also became a challenge for the farmers and community stakeholders to commit themselves to an agreement that they might not see the full utilization yet at this point in time. The proponent has been challenged on how to explain the concept and context of this capstone to the end-users.

The Province of Occidental Mindoro has experienced and was hit by series of typhoons namely Quinta, Rolly, and Ulysses. The local officials as well as the CP team were preoccupied with their official duties to address the state of calamity.

With the above cited challenges, the team tried as soonest as possible to reschedule the consultative meeting given the time frame of capstone implementation. Intense advocacy campaign were instigated to make them realize the importance of this impact study.

The proponent confronted financial restraints for the mobilization of the team. The problem of logistic support from NFA was considerable and expected since the agency was in the middle of transition due to the implementation of RA 11203 or the Rice Tariffication Law. Yet in order to accomplish this journey, the research proponent utilize his personal fund. Some of the team members also contribute to gain common fund for mobilization. There were members who lend their personal cars to service the team.

Finally, the limited time frame given to finish a full-length paper has also posed a challenge to the proponent. On top of this paper were also the bulk of work he has to do as a professional in his own field of work.

Conclusions

The main concerns of this study were taken from the results derived from the focus group discussions and series of consultative meetings with the administration of the NFA, the BGLUs and MGLUs; and the community stakeholders.

The first problem that is addressed in this capstone is the identification of the different measures being utilized by the NFA to respond to the insufficiency of storage areas for palay during and even after procurement.

Accordingly, the measures that were done by the NFA prior to the conduct of this study were the following:

- the sustaining of NFA-owned warehouses;

- leasing of buying stations or in extreme cases and as a need arise – the outside piling;
- periodically conducting Farmers' Ugnayan prior to the onset of harvest season;
- coordinating with the rice millers;
- the aggressive distribution or sales approaches; and
- domestic transfer-out of rice to highly dependent areas.

The second problem that is further addressed are the recognition of possible collaborations between the NFA and the community to safeguard the volume of production by local farmers to allow the food agency to utilize the available infrastructure of the local government as procurement and storage facility.

These collaborations are identified as follows:

- The forging of public-private partnerships. The proponent was able to forge an official agreement with the LGUs of SAMARICA, Occidental Mindoro through its community leaders public-private partnerships - The proponent was also able to forge an official agreement with the LGUs of SAMARICA, Occidental Mindoro through its community leaders; and the
- The creation of a farmers' sector empowerment plan in terms of the crafting of guidelines on good warehouse keeping and quality management - this was part of the deliverables that was for the adoption of the agency and partner communities.

To address the third problem, the researcher articulated the following interventions and innovations from both private and government that becomes significant to creation of his proposed Action Plan and Program (APP). These are the following:

- Conduct economic development campaign.
- Invitation to other BGUs and MLGUs in order to improve the current status of warehousing of palay during and even after procurement seasons.
- Development and implementation of the Community Collaborative Plan for Buffer Stock Storage as well as the monitoring of feedback will be formed part of the sustainability plan.
- Apply a proactive approach of orientation coupled with positive advocacy drive that can achieve a collaborative governance and synergies among the stakeholders to face the challenges in the public sector.

In order that the project becomes sustainable, the following are the recommendations:

To encourage other LGUs into entering to the same MOA to ensure that the project becomes a commonality to all communities. This will allow the farmers and community stakeholders to become active participants into achieving the common purpose of addressing the issue on stock piling of palay during procurement and post-procurement seasons.

To educate the local farmers to become competitive because of RTL- like developing more innovative marketing strategies of their produce. At the other end, this is to encourage farmers to get into another source of livelihood other than farming. This economic shift has been done by Japan, from their being agricultural into manufacturing and production society. This change has made them get into a better economy.

To recommend to Department of Agriculture through MAOs to capacitate local farmers into exploring other means of capitalization, not only for their farm inputs and machineries but also to allow them to provide their own the storage facilities that will help the NFA to address the problems of stockage.

To further devise a Collaborative Plan, enjoining all other local agencies into innovating current practices.

To elevate this Sustainability Plan to the NFA Regional and Central Office for the adoption of other branches and replicate the undertakings of the Occidental Mindoro branch.

Strategic Implications to Development Management

For this capstone project to be evaluated as a success, the deliverable outputs that were recommended have been directed towards constructing and realizing a better development management of the agency. Along this line of thought, this capstone ensured that there must be sufficient strategic planning; and that, the administration and control of the said outputs should have been upon the commencement of the initial project planning; all through its pre-implementation, implementation, and post-implementation phases. All of which were done in consideration to the needs, capacities, and capabilities of the communities.

Aside from that, all those activities that were undertaken, were geared towards the interest of creating a citizen-centric plan. In portraying the citizen-centric program that was carried-out, it included the formulation of agreement that hoped to secure the highest interest for the good of the community stakeholders, who were hardest hit by the Rice Tarrification Law. In the making of the guidelines, the topographical situation in Mindoro plus the scarcity of needed resources were also highlighted. These were great considerations by the proponent in making logical recommendations for the concerns regarding the problems set forth by the community and the NFA.

Nevertheless, the organization productivity has also been a priority concern in the implementation of the said action planning to make

sure that all other concerns are addressed accordingly. Having highlighted the seeming scarcity of resources and all other technicalities of appropriating existing capabilities of both the communities and the agency regarding this current issue, this capstone paved the way to make possible ways of making sure that all strategies and plans are directed towards the main goal of the study – to provide answers to the issues and problems that have been identified in the most efficient, productive, and realistic ways.

Development management would always be affected by how strong-willed the communities and their partner agency (NFA) are to adhere to what have been agreed upon in the memorandum that they have signed between and among themselves; and the strategic implications that go with it. Now, there is assurance that NFA has community partners to achieve its mandate of buffer stocking and on the same time to accommodate the produce of our local farmers. This capstone project shows how innovation emerged through collaborative efforts of NFA with the communities. That this kind of simple yet community partnering project could have high impact to the development particularly in agricultural sector despite lack of resources.

References

- ADB. (2012). , “Sector Assessment: Agriculture and Natural Resources”, Philippines: Country Operations Business Plan (2013-2015). Retrieved from www.adb.org/sites/default/files/linked-documents/cobp-phi-2013-2015-ssa-04.pdf
- ADB. (2012). Philippines Transport Sector Assessment, Strategy, and Roadmap. Asian Development Bank.
- Ansell, C., & Gash, A. (2007). Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*.
- Battini, D. (2008). Dynamic Modeling for Networks and Logisitics Complex Systems.
- Briones R.M and Felipe J. (2013). “Agriculture and Structural Transformation in Developing Asia: Review and Outlook”. Retrieved from www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/30380/ewp-363.pdf
- CFS. (2015). Global Strategic Framework on Food Security and Nutrition.,
- DA. (2015). Summary of 2010-2015 Funded R&D Projects, Department of Agriculture.
- Dansal, J. (2019). National Food Authority: New Roles. Grains.
- David, C. (1997). “Philippine Agriculture’s Institutional Structure of Governance: A Critique”. Retrieved from <http://dirp3.pids.gov.ph/ris/dps/pidsdps9712.pdf>
- Emerson, Kirk, Nabartchi, T., & Balogh, S. (2012). An Integrative Framework for Collaborative Governance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*.
- FAO. (2014). The State of Food Insecurity in the World. Strengthening the Enabling Environment for Food Security and Nutrition. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i4030e.pdf>
- Green, K.W., Whitten, D., & Inman, R.A. (2008). The impact of logistics performance on organizational performance in a supply chain context. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 13 (4), 317-327.
- Llanto, G. (2013). “The Impact of Infrastructure on Agricultural Productivity”: Productivity Growth in Philippine Agriculture.
- Lovgren, C. & Orrskog, E. . (2012). Improving the procurement process for better warehouse utilization.
- Manalili N.M., Yaptenco K.F. and Manilay A.A. (2015). “Rapid Appraisal of the Postharvest Facilities Projects in the Philippines. Retrieved from <http://dirp3.pids.gov.ph/webportal/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1531.pdf>
- Murthy, D.N. & Blischke, W. (2006). Warranty Management and Product Manufacture. Springer Series in Reliability Engineering. Springer.
- Navarro A. and Llanto G.M. (2014). “Financing Infrastructure in the Philippines: Fiscal Landscape and Resources Mobiliation”. Retrieved from <http://dirp3.pids.gov.ph/webportal/CDN/PUBLICATIONS/pidsdps1401.pdf>.
- NEDA. (2011). Philippine Development Plan 2011-2016.
- OECD. (2016). OECD Investment Policy Reviews: Philippines 2016. OECD Publishing.
- Olarte, R. (2016). NFA's "loss" is social cost. *Grains*, 5-6.
- PSA. (2014). 2014 Philippine Statistical Yearbook.
- PSA. (2015). 2015 Philippine Statistical Yearbook.
- Quigley, J.M. & Robertson, K.L. (2015). Configuration Management: Theory, practice and application.
- Reyes C.M., Tabuga A.D., Asis R.D. and Datu M.B G. (2012). “Poverty and Agriculture in the Philippines: Trends in Income Poverty

and Distribution". Retrieved from <http://dirp4.pids.gov.ph/ris/dps/pidsdps1209.pdf>

Sombilla M.A., Lantican F.A. and Beltran J.C. (2006). "Securing Rice, Reducing Poverty: Challenges and Policy Directions" Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture.

Thomas, T. (2015). "A Biophysical Approach to Modelling Alternative Agricultural Futures Under Climate Change", Chapter 10 in *The Future of Philippine Agriculture, Scenarios, Policies and Investments under Climate Change*.

Tobias, Molina, Valera, Mottaleb, and Mohanty. (2012). *Handbook on Rice Policy in Asia*, International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), Philippines. Retrieved from http://books.irri.org/9789712202858_content.pdf

UN. (2015). *Millenium Development Goals: 2015 Progress Chart*.

UNDP. (2010). *Evaluation of UNDP contribution to strengthening local governance participation*, UNDP Evaluation Office.

UNDP, UN Habitat, Global Taskforce of Local and Regional Governments for Post-2015 Development Agenda Towards Habitat III. (2014). *Localizing the Post-2015 Development Agenda: Dialogues on Implementation*, United Nations Development Group.

Villamar, D. (2017). *Factors Affecting the Absorption Rate of Institutionalized Procurement Program of NFA in SAMARICA*. Occidental Mindoro, Philippines.

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